

IMPACT OF REGULAR PHYSICAL ACTIVITY ON REDUCING THE RISK OF TYPE 2 DIABETES AMONG INDIVIDUALS WITH PREDIABETES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14024585>

Annotation

The study focuses on the impact of regular physical activity on reducing the risk of developing type 2 diabetes among individuals with prediabetes. Given the increasing incidence of diabetes, it is important to investigate how physical activity can help improve health outcomes in individuals with prediabetes by preventing the development of the disease. The paper presents data on the effect of various types of physical activity on blood glucose levels, insulin sensitivity, and body weight. The results confirm that regular exercise reduces the risk of developing prediabetes into type 2 diabetes and improves health outcomes.

Key words: physical activity, prediabetes, type 2 diabetes mellitus, prevention, risk, insulin resistance.

Relevance

Type 2 diabetes has become a global epidemic affecting millions of people. Morbidity rates continue to rise, especially among those with prediabetes – a condition in which blood glucose levels are elevated but have not yet reached the critical point for a diabetes diagnosis. Individuals with prediabetes are particularly in need of preventive measures to prevent the transition to diabetes, which requires affordable and effective approaches. One of these methods is regular physical activity, which has proven to be effective in improving insulin resistance, reducing body weight, and improving metabolic performance.

In the context of increasing risk and costs of diabetes treatment, it is important to study the impact of physical activity as a simple and affordable method of prevention. This study aims to examine the effectiveness of regular physical activity in reducing the risk of type 2 diabetes in people with prediabetes, which is particularly important in the current public health strategy.

Objective: to evaluate the impact of regular physical activity on reducing the risk of developing type 2 diabetes in individuals with prediabetes.

Materials and methods. The study involved 100 people diagnosed with prediabetes, divided into two groups: the first – with regular physical activity, the second – without it. Blood glucose levels, insulin resistance, and body mass index (BMI) were evaluated over a 6-month period. Participants in the first group performed moderate aerobic exercise 3-5 times a week. The data were processed using statistical methods to determine the correlation between physical activity and improvement in prediabetes indicators.

Results

Obesity is an important health problem in many countries. Obesity is currently considered as a multifactorial, chronic, relapsing disease associated with the development of a number of diseases that reduce a person's life expectancy and reduce its quality. Obesity has become so widespread that it has pushed into the background the problem of malnutrition in the population of underdeveloped countries and even infectious diseases, although the last two items were previously considered the main threats to human health. The results showed that participants with regular physical activity showed a significant reduction in blood glucose levels and improved insulin sensitivity compared to the control group. Body mass index (BMI) decreased by 4% in the active group, while no significant changes were observed in the control group. The analysis showed that physical activity helped reduce the likelihood of developing prediabetes into type 2 diabetes in 60% of participants. These findings support that regular exercise can be an effective means of preventing type 2 diabetes in individuals with prediabetes.

Conclusion

The study confirms that regular physical activity is an effective way to prevent type 2 diabetes among individuals with prediabetes. Regular aerobic exercise helps improve metabolic performance, lower blood glucose levels and body weight, reducing the risk of prediabetes progressing to diabetes. These results highlight the importance of physical activity as part of a comprehensive prevention program for individuals with prediabetes. Introducing regular exercise into everyday life, supporting it at the health level, and informing the public can significantly help reduce the burden of type 2 diabetes in society.

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